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THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION TO WORK FOR THE INCREASE OF EFFICIENCY

РОЛЬ МОТИВАЦИИ ТРУДА ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ

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Abstract. In this article the essence of concepts of workers and their attitude to labor, the motivation of the labor, promoting and influencing on motivations of the mechanism in the enterprises on the market–economic attitudes are theoretically investigated. Also, scientific conclusions and offers of the result of practical researchs carried out on the improvement of attitudes of labor and motivation of labor for an increase of efficiency of labor are revealed.

Аннотация. В статье теоретически исследована сущность мотивации труда, стимулирование и влияние на мотивацию рыночно–экономических отношений на предприятиях. А также, научные заключения и предложения результатов практических исследований, выполненных с целью усовершенствования отношений и мотивации для повышения эффективности труда.

Keywords: efficiency of labor, motivation, stimulations, management efficiency of labor, the norm of labor, labor attitudes, wages.

Ключевые слова: эффективность труда, мотивация, стимулирование, управление эффективностью труда, нормы труда, трудовые отношения, заработная плата.

The social and economic structure of Uzbekistan undergoes today qualitative changes, it is necessary to touch the sphere of labor attitudes. The social and economic position of the worker at the enterprise varies, its attitude to carried out work, the motivation of labor activity changed also.

Any economic way is based on the certain system of the values accepted by a great bulk of the population. Economic reforms are carried out when they create the new system of values perceived by the population adequate to them. Otherwise transformations mention the only superficial layer of social and economic attitudes and, in the queue, “conversed”, transformed by weights with reference to the system of sights accepted by them.

Economic transformations spent at us, as a rule, are carried out to accounts of the uzbek’s, welfare stereotypes coincide with the system of values inherent in them and motives of activity.

Materials and Methods

The theoretical substantiation of the change of the attitude to labor, labor ethics as a whole at fundamental social and economic shifts has been made by Maks Veber at the end of the XIX — the beginning of the XX c. [1, p. 48]. Developing these ideas, D. Makklelland [2] on the big empirical material demonstrated the dependence of economic successes of a society on a condition of labor motivation.

With reference to the problems of management of labor questions of labor motivation was analyzed in a different context by such scientists as A. Maslou [3, p. 114], K. Levin [4, p. 247] and etc.

Influence on the motivation of labor activity with a view of the increase of efficiency of alive

labor has received development at that stage of the market economy which has been connected to the mass use of wage, i.e. at an industrial stage of development of capitalism. The labor market, with its goods — a labor — predetermined concentration of attention of managers on one of the groups of the motives regulating labor activity of the person, namely on motives of material compensation for labor.

Absolutizations of material stimulation as a method of management of labor, that circumstance promoted also, that wage in mass production was mainly simple, not demanding high qualification. To adjust it was necessary, first of all, its quantitative side — the volume of made production. As to quality only the conformity of the established norm achievable by a sense of duty of the worker here was required.

The essence of the approach to the subject of labor activity — to the worker — at the beginning of conveyor manufacture is aphoristically expressed in the words, attributed to the G. Ford: “The best worker is well trained monkey” [5, p. 7].

The price–labor payment in its various variants at the obligatory control over the quality of carried out operations successfully coped with tasks of management of efficiency of labor. In the same cases when from the worker performance of the difficult operations which are not carrying mass character was required, various forms of a time wage were used.

The second half of the XX centuries was marked, on less to a measure, two events in economic development: the transition from the industrial type of economy to postindustrial and globalization of economic processes.

The postindustrial economy in the advanced countries has led to the reduction of number occupied in mass production and to moving of a labor to the area of intellectual labor.

Simple labor gives in to mechanical replacement. As K. Turov, professor of Massachusetts Institute of Technology in Boston wrote, “uneducated, untrained, unqualified so, and not capable of people for creative work, will push aside cheaper and exact machines” [6].

Half of economic growth from fiftieth years of our century has been caused by scientific researches and technologies. In the near future of knowledge will cost more, than army and arms.

The nearest decades in the foreground of a historical stage there are those countries, those peoples which will be capable of providing a higher level of erudition, good breedings, skill in all its displays, and certainly morals and culture.

Transition to the postindustrial economy it is necessary to show new requirements to labor potential of a labor. In postindustrial economy to create riches creative activity is capable only. And integrally to be entered in this economy those countries which workers can accept this call are capable only.

If in the industrial economy the basic attention was given psychophysiological and to the vocational components of the labor potential providing necessary intensity and set the quality of labor in the postindustrial economy the special importance is got with motivational (personal) potential of the worker.

The priority qualities providing competitiveness on a labor market, to become high qualified, the ability to innovations, the initiative and creative attitude to the work, directly connected with the motivation of work.

Base motives of labor activity are universal for all epoch and cultures. Within the framework of various types of economic activities the structure of universal motives varies, the motivational potential showing a level of opportunities, connected with the force of development of corresponding promptings to labor activity is formed characteristic for the given type. It reaches maintenance of high economic results within the framework of the given cultural — economic type with its semantic orientation and the proclaimed purposes.

Management hired work is carried out by a combination of methods of compulsion and prompting. It is connected to the character of motivation. Depending on the force of motives the motivation can be directed or on the preservation of the achieved level of the social status of the worker, including its such characteristics as a material well–being, a degree of realization of labor potentialities, self-affirmation and public utility of results of work; or on the achievement of higher

status.

In the first case the worker limits the efficiency of the activity to that measure which allows him to keep achieving a level, i.e. carries out the caused norm of work. In the second — he maximizes labor efforts.

It is obvious, that at orientation to the preservation of the status the worker practically does not react to stimulation. The management efficiency is reduced by work in this case to maintenance of performance of the established norms of work as orientation to preservation of the status (motivation of preservation) assumes minimization of labor expenses.

For use of stimulation as a method of increase of efficiency of work, orientation of the worker to achievement of higher status (motivation of achievement) is necessary.

The choice of this or that type of motivation depends, first of all, on the valuable orientations specifying the purposes and determining sense of labor activity.

Development of effectual measures of strengthening of interest in effective work of hired workers is possible only on a modern scientific basis, on knowledge and understanding of real mechanisms of functioning of system of motivation of work and its interaction with factors industrial medium in concrete welfare circumstances.

Mechanical loans foreign models of effective motivational management have already proved the inconsistency during economic reforms by virtue of specificity and even uniqueness of the real labor attitudes having a place to be in our reformed society.

Before to start the analysis of mechanisms of functioning of labor motivation in market conditions, it is necessary to define a circle of concepts with which we shall operate, and to formulate some general provisions, leaning on which it is possible to build logic designs of these mechanisms.

As the problem of motivation of work lays in the planes of several sciences and does not belong to actually economic science, we shall formulate a line of axioms on which we shall base, meaning thus, that their proof, — a prerogative of social psychology, sociology and of some other scientific disciplines.

The first axiom will be, that the motivation of work is a part of system of motivation of activity and is most closely connected to its such components as economic and consumer motivations.

The following position accepted by us as an axiom, will be, that motivation of labor at least, on valuable (axiom's) a level, is formed in the process socialization persons prior to the beginning of labor activity. The leading part of formation of labor motivation social values and norms, long-term (strategic) purposes (meaning of the life), and also psychophysiological features of the person.

The third axiom says, that the social essence of motivation of work can be opened on the basis of such elements of determination of labor activity, as needs, interests, valuable orientations, social norms, social installations, the purposes and programs of activity.

The fourth axiom consists of that idea of the person are the empirical facts and give in to the scientific analysis. This position is proved by a line of foreign philosophers [7, p. 107].

At last, a fifth accepted axiom, says, that research of motivation proceeds from representation about heterogeneity of consciousness, it two-layer. Thus, the first layer — operationally — technical, concentrates on direct practical activities whereas the second (the reflective layer) — has axiom's (valuable) character and operates in wider time prospect [8, p. 182].

Results and Discussion

The basic concepts which are used in the analysis mechanisms motivations, essence: motive, motivation, a motivational nucleus, motivational potential, and also definitions describing them — riches, force, an orientation, a level of claims.

The motive — is the realized prompting to activity. It will consist of the following components: need (interest); the blessing, capable to satisfy the given need [9, p. 201]; the expenses necessary for reception the blessings (activity); and the price, as result of comparison of the received blessing and the expenses (costs) connected to it.

Schematically of motive can be presented in the following kind (Figure):

Figure. Schematically a kind of motive.

It is necessary to emphasize, that as the same need can be satisfied with the various blessings, and the same blessing is capable of satisfying various needs. Thus, a link between need and the blessing can be various kinds of activity, and the price includes not only economic, and the physiological, psychological, moral, aesthetic and other costs connected to assignment of the blessing.

The motivation — is the interconnected set of all motives inducing the person to activity. It represents complete structure with difficult interrelations between elements making it. As in any system, its properties cannot be shown to properties of elements making it. The motives which are included in system, form a difficult configuration in which there are a nucleus and periphery.

The motivational nucleus of the person — set of the motives mutually conditioned understanding by motive of activity, internal determinant of the behaviour, determining its general orientation.

The motivational nucleus is basically criterion at definition such as motivation.

The type of motivation is a characteristic of motivational potential of the person or the group, reflecting semantic an orientation of labor activity on the satisfaction of the certain groups of needs.

Type of motivation mediated character and an orientation of the requirements showed by the worker to the industrial environment, an estimation of an opportunity of realization of these requirements, a degree of personal labor activity of the subject and the general satisfaction work.

It is necessary to distinguish motivational potential of economic culture and motivational potential of the subject of labor activity — industrial group or the separate worker.

The motivational potential of economic culture expresses a level of development of those valuable orientations which provide high economic results, a level of opportunities of activation of labor activity which carry in itself social institutes, characteristic for the certain economic culture.

The motivational potential of the subject of labor activity (the worker or industrial group of workers) are those opportunities of activation of labor efforts which can be realized during stimulation of labor activity.

The motivation of work is formed in that and only in the event that actual needs for the person and their satisfying blessings are connected with labor activity.

It is possible to allocate with a method of the logic analysis four groups of base needs which satisfaction can be carried out by means of labor activity.

The first group — the needs connected to pithiness of labor. These are needs for the work interesting to the given person, allowing to realize the knowledge, skills, skills in the certain independence at a choice of ways and means of work; in an opportunity of innovations and to improvement of professional skill corresponding to them, i.e. self-development during labor activity.

The second group — needs in performance social and economic significant kinds of labor

activity. This group of motives is closer than others is connected to semantic filling of labor, and its concrete maintenance is interpreted in a cultural context.

Work in various cultures has various semantic filling.

In China where the culture is based on confucianism, the sense of labor activity will consist of achievement of the order in Celestial. All system of social and economic values and appropriate it of the institutes regulating labor activity, is directed on eradication of spirit of a profit in separate people and enrichment of the state.

In the Islamic states sense of labor activity — perfect—souls for occurrence in a heavenly empire. Here very personal enrichment is not encouraged. The accent of system of values is put on “maintenance of a circle of validity” — taxation and distributive attitudes.

In Europe the system of values authorized labor activity and aspiration to material riches. Accordingly the purpose of work became reception of the profit, accumulation of the capital, maximization of a public product for satisfaction of needs of weights.

The history shows, that there where labor activity was considered mainly as necessity for satisfaction of needs of nature, there was a minimization of labor expenses, technical progress remained in embryo. At the same time there, where the purpose of work proclaimed maximization of the profit, accumulation of riches, rough growth of an intensification of labor activity was observed.

The Economic progress of the West in many respects has been provided with development of those social institutes which encouraged strong motivation to high—efficiency work.

In the general view semantic filling of work in various cultures can be reduced to the following aspects: the attitude to work as to a public duty, regardless of what it is necessary to make; as to the useful activity connected to release of production necessary for people; at last, as to the activity, satisfying demand for those or other kinds of the goods.

The special value of this group of motives will be, that its place in structure of motivation defines an orientation “on itself” or “on others” and by that predetermines the attitude to consumer properties of made production. The market economy is focused on the consumer. Force of these motives and their place in the structure of motivation, alongside with the attitude to the labor as to the goods, can serve as the indicator of a degree of transition to market motivation of labor.

The third group — the needs connected with maintenance of means of existence, reproduction of the person. These are needs for a payment, earnings for maintenance of the certain prosperity for the family; in satisfaction of those social needs with which for whatever reasons not always it is possible to satisfy for money.

The fourth group of needs — status the needs connection about position of the worker in reviewer for it to the social group. It is possible to attribute needs for dialogue, a recognition (respect), service promotion (career) to them.

Each of these groups of needs can become rod (force of motivation), main around of which the motivational nucleus of the person is formed to define understanding motive of labor.

Force of motivation — is a total intensity of desire to satisfy significant needs. The level of force of motivation allows allocating motivation of achievement and motivation of preservation.

The motivation of achievement is directed on the development of new needs and expansion of a spectrum of the blessings, their satisfying. It a source of development of labor activity.

The motivation of preservation is directed on maintenance and preservation of the achieved level of satisfaction of needs and supports labor activity at that level which allows avoiding the sanctions directed on restriction or reduction of quantity of the received blessings.

A line of the conditions connected to freedom of a choice is necessary for formation of motivation of achievement. First, the society should authorize a high level of vital standards (quality of a life here and now). Second, it should have a variety of the blessings attractive to the individual. Thirdly, the individual should have confidence that these blessings are accessible to it that it can receive them as a result of the labor activity. At last, the costs connected to their purchase, should be for it comprehensible. Only at presence of these necessary conditions the motivation of achievement providing high labor activity and, accordingly, efficiency of labor can be

generated.

And still preservation of value of work as socially normal way of satisfaction of needs, allows a capitalist society to avoid disintegration and to proceed on new step developments — from industrial to postindustrial economy where the rate is done on difficult labor, with domination of the creative beginning and ability to innovations.

We have approached economy to the period of market reforms with physically decaying labor, compelled to function in the adverse industrial environment; with the system of the payment which is not providing its normal reproduction. The irresponsible squandering of labor, characteristic for administrative — scheduled system, destroyed officially declared semantic filling of labor activity — labor for the blessing of a society. The system of distributive attitudes did not provide realization statusion needs worker [10].

It does not mean, that the population of Uzbekistan works less. The reforms which have sharply lowered a standard of life of people, have caused necessity of higher expenditures of labor for maintenance of ability to live.

Adaptation to new conditions of existence went on several basic channels.

One of them — activization of work in housekeeping. It is work on horticulture and vegetables the sites, providing for many families food resources in conditions of regular nonpayments of wages.

Researches have revealed features of motivation of labor activity of the workers included in market attitudes. First of all, at them another attitude to a life, other social state of health is formed. They in the majority are satisfied with a life, are sure to tomorrow's day, ready to take up the responsibility for own well-being. In other words, they are distinguished by the general positive adjust, whereas at the enterprises which have preserved former system of attitudes, such adjust more often negative and at a significant part of workers the phenomenon of social weariness is fixed.

The second feature — high represented motivations of achievement, high force of motives. And it is a source of labor activity. Thus, the highest force is marked at motives of professional growth, service promotion and compensation. Last circumstance confirms the idea stated earlier, that absence among priority values of work of high payment at employment carries sociocultural character: a print in mass consciousness of social norm of the recent past when social — prestigious work for the sake of “the light future” was proclaimed, instead of for the sake of earnings.

The third feature — on the general background of high force of groups of the motives directed “on itself”: motives of pithiness of work, compensation for work and status motives, — weak force of motives “for others”, providing consumer cost, and, hence, and opportunities of selling, competitiveness of the made goods and services. This group of motives always in our conditions stood in structure of motivation in last place, contrary to official propagation. As have shown researches, a syndrome reversion to labor motivation “on itself”, alongside with low force of innovative motives, appeared at transition to the market the most proof and demanding special efforts for its overcoming.

At last, it is impossible to ignore such feature, as a choice of an image of preferable work. For the personnel the surveyed enterprises two preferable images are characteristic: a hard work with dynamical earnings dependent on personal efforts, and various work with the unexpected situations, demanding high professionalism, at a guaranteed level of payment.

Development of market attitudes in labor sphere, transition to the real wage labor, determined in the image influences a condition of labor motivation, approaching it to market type.

To market economy priorities remain general reorientation of labor motivation to market character of labor attitudes: formation at the hired worker of the attitude to the labor as to the goods having consumer cost; and neutralization of the norms legalized during reforms and the rules of shadow economy regulating behaviour of the worker on manufacture.

The decision of the first task is solved through optimum realization of all functions of wages. The decision of the second — by means of use of rigid administrative — legal methods of management.

There, where high technologies are not required, accordingly, there is no necessity for rich and strong motivation of labor, realizing creative and innovative potentialities of the person. For reception of the necessary results, correctly enough organized material stimulation of labor activity in a combination of the rigid administrative control, to use of imperious prompting to labor.

If the rate is done on development of the manufacture based on high technologies, with an exit in space of postindustrial economy, the success will be predetermined by opportunities of motivation of workers, i.e. change of their motivational potential. It is a task of another level of the complexity, demanding another strategy of management. Here, on the basis of maintenance of full realization reproductive functions of wages, in stimulation the accent should be put on such the organization and working conditions which would expand borders of self-organizing of labor activity and strengthened the personal responsibility of the worker for quality.

Necessary condition of efficiency as stimulations, and motivations is maintenance of full realization reproductive functions of a payment.

As a rule the wages are allocated according to three basic functions: reproductive, stimulating and statusion. A line of researchers allocates also stabilizing function, seeing its assignment in fastening workers on a workplace by an establishment with it of the increased size of a payment.

The leading role belongs reproductive to function. Refusal of a policy of a cheap labor — a necessary condition of transition of the mass worker from installation on “guaranteed payment at minimization of labor efforts” to market installation on “the maximal payment at the maximal labor efforts”. Without formation of such installation cannot be and speeches about market type of motivation of labor.

Maintenance of realization in full reproductive functions of wages — a necessary condition of market reorientation of motivation of work and formation of the labor morals providing a high level of labor activity and quality of labor.

Realization reproductive is necessary for function of wages and that in practice of management began possibly to use stimulating and statusion functions of a payment. Thus it is important to balance actually not so much cost and the price of a labor, they equal only in an ideal, how many to provide its conformity to social and economic norm.

Researches show, that a level of claims of workers to fair, in their opinion, a wage is that threshold for which stimulating function of a payment starts to work. Any increase in the salary in borders from its actual size up to a level of claims on validity does not possess stimulating effect, as is perceived by the worker only as restoration of the trampled validity.

Refusal of the rate on a cheap labor could untie many units in economy. However, increase of average wages up to a share of wages in productivity of the advanced countries, as well as minimization of taxes, is direct or indirectly connected with the wages, necessary, but not yet sufficient measure.

The second condition consists that realization of stimulating function of wages and consequently also its influence on efficiency of work, cannot be provided without an establishment of rigid connection between size of earnings and quantity and quality of the spent work.

Statusion function of wages consists that the worker perceives it as a social estimation of the importance of the labor. This estimation is most important for those workers who sees the basic sphere of self-realization of the personal potentialities in labor activity, and, accordingly, sphere of self-affirmation. As a rule, it is the most active, productive and creative workers.

Mechanisms inside and interprofessional social comparison to them are not only much more strongly advanced, than at workers with tool labor motivation, but also based on other criteria.

At tool motivation the basic criterion of comparison — a level of a material well-being. The worker of this type brings to a focus on the general size of earnings. the relation that its part which is directly defined by the labor contribution, with what does not depend on it, it is not perceived as significant.

At the motivation based on self-realization and self-affirmation in work, base criterion of comparison — conformity of a measure of work and a measure of its payment as a recognition of a society of the social — labor status of the worker. In this case the accent is put on validity. The

attention is accented on that part of earnings which is directly connected hardly, various surcharges possess stimulating effect only in the event that they allocate the worker from a lump, emphasize and consolidate its status.

Taking into account, that the type of motivation of the worker only mediated is connected to the type of manufacture or a field of activity, the policy of stimulation of labor activity in any manufacture should versification in view of the personal factor. Methods and measures of stimulation can give positive result only in the event that they noted features of motivational type of the worker.

The correct organization of stimulation — a basis of efficiency of motivation of workers. Just because the payment is perceived and as a recognition of the social status as the form of a social estimation, it shows and fixes in consciousness of workers that quality which are most significant for the employer.

Differently, by means of a payment come to light really functioning, and not just professed social norms and the priorities regulating labor activity. It and norms — samples, following which is encouraged, and norms — interdiction, infringement which is punished.

Conclusion

As a result resulted theoretical analysis researches show, that the creative beginnings in work are directly connected with the opportunities of self-regulation of intensity of labor, with expansion of sphere of freedom of the worker as conditions of growth of labor activity. For development of initiative, innovative and creative forms of labor behaviour the rigid labor discipline as creativity and the initiative of the worker directly produce it sense of duty is contra-indicated and do not demand on imperious methods of prompting to work.

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